

Impact Measurement and Application of Conservation (IMACS)

1. Abstract

This article describes a system for the calculation of environmental (E) and human condition (H) impacts and sustainabilities for all products, services and individuals as a set of universally standardized methods, earlier published as a patent application (1). The overall system allows buyers to select more sustainable products and services, and allows end-user consumers to apply conservation rendering the product or service purchased free of damaging environ-human (EH) impacts. It includes EH impacts contributed by employees and other parts of the organization. The system carries EH impact variables through the supply chain as an extension of the price variables “currency” and “monetary amount”. Similar to the calculation and payment of prices and salaries, the system runs in real time and allows calculation of EH impacts at very low costs. The system has the potential to create very large amounts of funding for conservation, may prevent nature from being pushed past tipping points from which no return is possible (2) and potentially allows a relative fast return to pre-industrial environmental conditions, while improving human conditions and saving costs.

2. Introduction

A sustainable lifestyle and sustainable production of goods and services are becoming increasingly important. A large number of methods are published and/or used for sustainability measurement of organizations (3). Such reporting is retrospective and typically annually. These systems are not designed for sustainability measurement of goods, services or individuals. Different products and services require different inputs of materials, energy and employee labor. For each of these inputs, the environmental and human impacts vary and will change over time. Ultimately all products and services are consumed by end-user consumers. In order to become (more) sustainable, end-user consumers must be able to select (increasingly more) sustainable products and services (4). For products and services, two sustainability measurement systems were developed over the last decades: Product Lifecycle Assessment (P-LCA) (5) and environmentally extended input-output life-cycle assessment (EEIO-LCA) (6). LCA is widely applied to building products. The limited number of E-impacts currently used could be expanded and it could be applied to all products (7). However, LCA methods use historic E-impact averages for their inputs and do not reflect EH-impact differences in supply routes and distributing organizations. With the transitioning to carbon neutrality and prevention of other negative Impacts, LCA methods cannot quickly catch improvements made along the supply chain. Calculation of EH-impacts using classic LCA for all products for all brands sold would also represent significant costs. In addition, LCA methods exclude human condition (H) impacts, ignore EH-impacts of the labor used, and do not assign costs to damaging EH-impacts, providing little incentive for improvement. No universal method exists measuring EH impacts and EH sustainabilities, for all products, services and individuals, in a universally standardized way, in real time and low costs along their paths through the supply chain while applying conservation.

3. The IMAC System

Humans use two types of resources; environmental (E) and human (H). With their actions, humans can have two types of impacts; impacts on the environment (E) and impacts affecting human conditions (H). Humans, as one of the species on Earth, should be considered as part of the environment; however, impacts on the environment and impacts affecting human conditions are usually treated separately. The combination of environmental and human conditions impacts caused directly or indirectly by humans are referred to as *environ-human* or *EH-conditions* and *EH-impacts*. EH-impacts can be neutral, negative (damaging) or positive (conserving/rehabilitating). Neutral impacts represent the use of natural resources at or below *sustainable available levels* under conditions of sufficient

conservation. *EH damage* represents negative EH-impacts and represents EH-liabilities, (e.g. environmental pollution, wildlife area loss or fragmentation, carbon dioxide emissions, pollution and inhumane conditions like slavery, child labor and sweatshop conditions). Unless specifically addressing environmental or human conditions, the letters “E” and “H” are dropped. *Conservation* represents positive impacts and assets. Conservation can represent *protection, restoration/ rehabilitating* or both (e.g. liberation, rehabilitation and education of slaves, pollution remediation, wildlife area conservation, carbon sequestration). Resource use without sufficient resource protection or beyond sustainable available levels reflects a negative impact (damage) and creates a liability. The *Impact Measurement And Conservation System (IMACS)* was developed to measure impacts of goods, services and individuals, while applying conservation. The concept of IMACS is to (1st) measure impacts of goods and services offered for sale and (2nd) to apply sufficient amounts of conservation to neutralize damaging impacts. This latter step only takes place during the sales transaction to end-user consumers, such that the goods and services sold end up “free of impacts”. A few dozen impact variables are distributed over ten impact groups. The system was extended to measure human condition impacts and apply human conditions protection and rehabilitation (H-conservation), forming the eleventh impact group (table 1). Implementation will start with the easiest to measure impact variables. Besides labor hours worked and salary paid, many of the H-impacts are more difficult to measure and are likely to be introduced in later stages.

1	Biodiversity conservation	7	Coastal area use and conservation (protection from changes due to sea level rise)
2	Cultivated area use (all areas not protected for their biodiversity)	8	Atmospheric ozone layer damage and conservation
3	Climate change	9	Infectious disease prevention and mitigation
4	Fresh water use and conservation	10	Human reproduction
5	Soil and surface water acidification or pH change	11	Human conditions
6	Soil & sediment use and conservation		

Table 1: The eleven IMACS impact groups

Four types of impact variables are used: allowance, current damage, historic damage and conservation. Allowance variables reflect natural resource use for which a certain amount can be used for cultivated purposes as long as a sufficient amount of the same natural resource is conserved. Without sufficient conservation applied, the allowance amount is not “sustainable available”. This applies to area use (land and sea), water consumption and soil “consumption” (damage and loss). For each allowance variable the individual allowance is calculated as the global accessible and sustainable available amount divided by the global population. Any resource use in excess of the allowance or sustainable available amount defaults to current damage. Current damage variables reflect damage done since the reference date τ_0 . All current damage needs to be eliminated ASAP, while remaining amounts must be immediately restored (limited to availability of conservation). For example, an individual can convert his home to carbon neutrality using heat pumps and buy an electric car, all powered by roof mounted solar, but cannot yet buy carbon neutral groceries. The latter current damage impacts need to be restored by purchasing sequestered CO₂. Current damage is calculated and must be restored for each good and services purchased. This applies among others to carbon dioxide emissions, biodiversity loss and damage, water use above sustainable levels, soil damage or loss above sustainable levels and soil and surface water acidification. No allowances exist for current or historic damage variables. Historic damage variables reflect the accumulation of damage done prior to date τ_0 . To become sustainable and return to the best approximation of pre-industrial conditions, all historic damage needs to be restored ASAP. A minimum restoration requirement exists for historic damage and will be expressed on a per dollar spending basis. Current and historic damage variables and some of the allowance variables rely on the same types of conservation to allow sustainable use (e.g. wildlife area protection) or to neutralize damage done (e.g. wildlife area restoration and carbon sequestration). Currently none of the types of conservation required for use with IMACS are available in their required forms, while all types of conservation are likely to be in short supply during most of the global restoration period needed to reach pre-industrial conditions. This means that restoration requirements for historic damage can only be gradually increased while the capacities for the various types of conservation are ramped up. Impacts for goods, services and individuals are calculated using environmental supply chain steps (ESCS). All ESCS inputs and outputs reflect *impacts* not *impact rates* (EH impacts per unit time). EH impact balances apply for each ESCS. Three types of ESCSs exist: one for products & services, one for individuals and one for determination (“rating”) of unknown inputs to ESCSs (figures 1 to 6). For individuals an individual supply chain step (ISCS) is used, each representing a single individual and their labor product. The inputs are *location-based impacts (LBI)*, *Impacts of goods & services consumed* and the *employee’s/individual’s own human condition impacts* added. LBIs have no labor or salary components (e.g. carbon dioxide and methane emissions of landfills). For any input to an ESCS for which money is paid, the monies are ultimately paid as salary/income to individuals

and associated with labor hours worked. Such inputs fall under goods and services consumed. All salary earned flows out with products consumed. The outputs are individual sustainable absorption (ISA) and the labor output. Examples of ISCS and PSCS are given in figures 1 to 4, while a combined ISCS-PSCS is shown in figure 5.

Figure 1: ISCS reflecting reference conditions for cultivated area use (an allowance variable) using example values over a one-week period. Except for financial compensations paid, all Impacts flow from left (resources) to right (end-users) through the figure. L = labor hours worked (h), U = resources used (Ha.w), P = conservation applied (Ha.w) and C = salary paid (\$). To convert to EH impact rates, all values need to be divided by the period considered: L/w = labor intensity (h/w), U/w = resource use rate (Ha), P/w = conservation rate (Ha) and C/w = salary rate (\$/w). Impacts of labor output are equal to the sum of all impact inputs minus the ISA impacts. Under reference conditions, the resource use is equal to the allowance, conservation applied is equal to requirements, while resource use and conservation applied leave the supply chain as ISA rendering the labor output free of impacts.

Use/damaging and protective/conserving impacts are respectively represented by variables U_m and P_n . Due to space limitations and the need to keep things simple, only one instance of variable U_m and one instance of variable P_n can be shown per figure. All impacts flow in end-use consumer direction (left to right) through the figures, while

Figure 2: PSCS corresponding to reference conditions for cultivated area use (an allowance variable) over a one-week period. The example represents N reference portfolios, each for all products consumed by a reference individual over a week. L = labor hours worked (h), U = resources used (Ha.w), P = conservation applied (Ha.w) and C = salary paid (\$). To convert to impact rates, all values need to be divided by period considered: L/w = labor intensity (h/w), U/w = resource use rate (Ha), P/w = conservation rate (Ha) and C/w = salary rate (\$/w). The multipliers E, S, L and N are used in combination with impact supply chain step variable notation $[L, U_m, P_n] | [C]$ where each multiplier operates at both sides of the vertical bar “|”. E = number of own employees, S = units of supplies, L = units of location-based-impact (LBI) while N is the number of products produced. The product impacts are equal to the sum of impact inputs minus the XID impacts. Under reference conditions, the impacts for U in the product output are equal to the sum of LBI and supplies resulting in zero XID impacts.

compensation paid (money paid for products purchased or as salary earned) flows in resource direction (right to left). A new notation is used to indicate impacts. This new ESCS notation uses square brackets and a vertical bar separating impact variables flowing in opposite directions: $[L, U, P] | [C]$. In figures, the value of each variable is listed below the corresponding variable letter, while arrows indicate the flow direction of the impacts. Impact variables are expressed as original variable values with units (like cultivated area used in Ha.y). Using the ESCS

notation, $[L, U, P] | [C]$ indicates the labor hours worked as “L”, the impacts of the specific resource use and damage variable used as “U”, the corresponding variable reflecting conservation applied as “P” and the compensation paid as “C”. In figures, the arrows below the variables in square brackets indicate the flow direction of impacts. Hundred percent sustainable conditions are referred to as “reference conditions”. Impacts can also be expressed as ratios (cultivated area used by an individual divided by the per capita cultivated area allowance) and are referred to as *normalized* (unit-less) variable conditions. To allow the required calculations, variables need to be *normalized* and are indicated using small letters in *Italic* font (figures 3-5), while capitals (in regular font) are

Figure 3: ISCS corresponding to normalized reference conditions for allowance and historic damage variables, reflecting the example values of figure 1. Under normalized conditions all variables are unit-less.

used for the original variables expressed in units. For allowance variable U_m the use of the individual allowance amount reflects 100% resource use sustainability for the resource variable. For historic damage variable U_m the application of the required amount of resource conservation reflects 100% conservation sustainability for the conservation variable. The impact notation can be expressed under normalized conditions as $[l, u_m, p_n] | [c]$ where $l = L / L_{Ref}$, $u_m = U_m / U_{m,Ref}$, $p_n = P_n / P_{n,Ref}$ and $c = C / C_{Ref}$. Variables L , U_m , P_n and C represent the original variable values as quantified. $U_{m,Ref}$ and $P_{n,Ref}$ represent the 100% *sustainable or reference values* for respectively the resource use allowance and the conservation required, while L_{Ref} and C_{Ref} are the *reference values* for hours worked and salary paid.

Figure 4: PSCS corresponding to normalized reference conditions for allowance and historic damage variables, reflecting the example values of figure 2. The multipliers E, S, L and N are used in combination with impact supply chain step variable notation $[l, u, p] | [c]$, where each multiplier operates at both sides of the vertical bar “|”. E = number of own employees, S = units of supplies, L = units of location-based impact, while N is the number of products produced. The EH impacts over the ISCS balance. Under reference conditions the XID is zero.

For current damage variables, the 100% sustainable condition is reached when no damage is done ($U_{m,Ref} = 0$) and no restoration is required ($P_{n,Ref} = 0$). $U_{m,Repr}$ (called *representative value*) represents the longer term average against which variable U_m is compared. The normalized conditions variable value for u_m is calculated by dividing the

current damage by the corresponding representative value ($u_m = U_m / U_{m,Repr}$). For example if the global per capita carbon (C) emissions are 5 ton carbon per year ($U_{C,Repr} = 5 \text{ tC/y}$), then the C-emission impact of an individual emitting 10 tC/y (or $U_C = 10 \text{ tC/y}$) would be calculated under normalized conditions as $u_C = U_C / U_{C,Repr} = (10 \text{ tC/y}) / (5 \text{ tC/y}) = 2$. See figure 5.

For ISCSs the individual sustainable absorption (ISA) block functions to remove conservation applied and sustainable available resources used from the supply chain to prevent accumulation. Under sustainable conditions, impacts for PSCSs can only originate from LBIs and supplies, since the impacts from employee labor are zero. Under non-sustainable conditions, inputs to the PSCS from LBIs and supplies are stored in goods and services produced and are in turn consumed by employees. On a global scale and without correction, this would lead to the same impacts traveling on average exactly twice through the global collection of PSCSs. For PSCSs the excess impact deduction (XID) block functions to remove any excess impacts from the supply chain that otherwise would create supply chain impact accumulation. Variables must be expressed in normalized form to calculate the ISA and XID, which are in turn needed to calculate the impacts of the labor output and products made. The normalized ESCS outputs values are then converted back to original variable values.

E-conservation is standardized per conservation impact variable (e.g. kg of CO₂ sequestered and m².d of wildlife area conserved) and made available in any fractional amount. Participating end-user consumers will be given access to “title-to-conservation” for each type of conservation on a per capita basis and based on global availability. An individual can participate by “signing-up” free of costs and using his/her participation ID (payment card, other). Conservation is automatically purchased during the sales process, by (and in name of) the end-user consumer, using electronic vouchers paid by the seller. The costs of the E-vouchers paid for by retailers are initially very low. For example, for 1 % customer participation, 1% participating products and cost of E-conservation equal to 12% of the product price, the cost for the retailer are $(0.12 * 0.01 * 0.01 =) 0.0012\%$. For E-voucher costs of \$ 12 per \$ 1 million sales, the retailer can advertise his products as “When you participate, we will pay all costs of your available E-conservation for participating products you buy”. In reality the costs to the retailer are even lower, since the participating customer has only access to a very small amount of conservation, simply because no more conservation is available. If only \$10 of conservation is available per participating consumer per month, this amount would be fully used in the above purchase, leaving no room to access other E-vouchers for other purchases that month. These costs are initially insignificant and not a reason to increase prices. However, the E-voucher costs will increase for higher participation rates, and the seller now has an incentive to select participating suppliers and to install carbon neutral systems in order to prevent such additional costs. All investments made to become carbon neutral, will be fully earned back by own and supply chain savings. The same applies to water use, biodiversity damage, soil loss, the use of labor under inhumane conditions and all other damaging impacts. Cost and savings aspects will be

Figure 5: Combined ISCS-PSCS representing one product of an organization and the employee labor used under reference normal conditions (100% sustainable) for a current damage variable. The ISCSs of the own employees are grouped in a group-ISCS. For grouped-ISCSs, the multiplier E is used for all inputs and outputs. For all ESCSs, the sum of LBI and products consumed / supplied must (and does) meet reference conditions.

presented in a separate paper. While the \$ 12 in conservation per million-dollar sales does not go very far in restoring Earth, the sum of all E-voucher amounts applied at any given time, are equal to the global conservation available. This is done by the IMACS organization daily increasing the “product participation rate”. The E-vouchers thus create a strong incentive for the global providers of conservation to increase their conservation capacity as fast as possible.

Impacts for LBIs need to be determined by an Impact Rating Organizations (IRO). The same applies to supplies and labor not already calculated as an ESCS output. Such determinations are carried out using a rating supply chain step (RSCS). See figures 6 and 7 under Methods. In those cases, LBIs and impacts of supplies, labor and goods & services that are inputs to ESCSs are estimated at very low costs using automated statistical EH-impact estimation methods. These estimation methods will be presented in a separate paper.

Currently all products and services have a price (say \$ 100), expressed by two variables; the currency used and the monetary amount to be paid. Under IMACS, all products, services and labor have a price A using an extended number of variables expressed as a collection of elements $A = \{a, b, c, \dots, z\}$, where a = product ID, b = currency, c = monetary amount and d to z are the impact variables of the eleven impacts groups. For a product for sale, d to j can be respectively labor hours worked, cultivated area (CA) used, wildlife area (WA) lost, CO₂ emitted, WA protected, WA restored and CO₂ sequestered. During each sales transaction to a participating end-user consumer, the unique product ID number tag is electronically read from the QR code, linking product i to its product data sheet and extracting the extended price data as the collection of elements A_i . During the transaction, all pertinent data are transmitted as a collection of elements $A_i = \{a, b, c, \dots, z\}$ between the seller’s terminal, the regional IMACS database and the debit/credit card or bank accounts of seller and buyer.

Product No. Purchased	Classic Price		IMACS Price Expressed as Collection of Elements $A = \{a, b, c, \dots, j\}$,								
	Currency	Amount	Currency	Amount	Labor Hours [h]	CA Used [m ² .y]	WA Lost [m ² .y]	CO ₂ Emitted [kgCO ₂]	WA Protected [m ² .y]	WA Restored [m ² .y]	CO ₂ Sequestered [kgCO ₂]
	b	c	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i	j
1	\$	100	\$	100	9.8	96	0.12	72.8	96	0.12	72.8
2	\$	300	\$	300	29.4	288	0.36	218.4	288	0.36	218.4
3	\$	200	\$	200	19.6	192	0.24	145.6	192	0.24	145.6
4	\$	150	\$	150	14.7	144	0.18	109.2	144	0.18	109.2
Total	\$	750	\$	750	73.5	720	0.90	546.0	124	0.90	546.0

Table 2: Example of products purchased by the end-user consumer during the selected accounting period using classic and IMACS price variables. IMACS prices are expressed as a collection of elements $A = \{a, b, c, \dots, j\}$, where a is the unique product ID (not shown), and b to j are the additional EH impact variables used. CA = cultivated area, WA is wildlife area. EH-impact values are calculated using CA use per \$ spent = 0.96 m².y/\$, WA lost per \$ spent = 0.0012 m².y/\$, CO₂ emissions = 0.73 kgCO₂/\$, labor hours = 0.098 h/\$ spending and a ratio $R_{Bio} = 1.0$. All required conservation is automatically applied during a 2nd purchase immediately following each primary purchase.

As shown in table 2, the values for each of the (in this example) seven additional Impacts are mathematically added for the four products just as the monetary variable values are added for the classic prices. No extra QR code scanning is required, while the additional calculation costs and time needed for the addition of the seven additional EH-impact variables are likely already negligible and will drop further in the future with faster and lower cost computing. Alternatively, only the product ID is transmitted as an additional value, while all EH-impact data are extracted from the product data sheets and communicated via different channels. At the end of the accounting period, the Impacts of the ISA and labor output are calculated. A similar process is used to calculate the Impacts of products and services, adding the LBI, supplies and labor assigned to each product series (or service), followed by the calculation of the XID and product Impacts. For Impacts assigned to PSCS within the same organization, data communication is limited to the seller’s terminals and the regional IMACS database. Otherwise identical products, part of the same production series, have identical Impacts immediately after production. However, use of different distributors and different shipping routes leads to different distribution related E-impacts and to different overall Impacts.

The IMAC system is based on voluntary participation. Both individuals and organizations can participate. Since no parts of the system (especially EH-conservation) currently exist in the forms needed, the system needs to be started and gradually grown to large and global participation over a 10 – 20-year period. Organizations/producers can in turn select which goods and services will participate, within a target fraction range set by the IMACS organization. All participating products and material supplies are QR barcoded using a proprietary coding system, while participating services provided and employee labor used are electronically documented using numbers corresponding to the same QR code system. All data handling and ESCS calculations are automated.

4. Results

For individuals the Impacts of the labor output are calculated using the ISCS. The process starts with collecting the inputs to the ISCS in their original variable form. An example for Cultivated Area use under reference conditions is given in table 3. Over a week's period the example reference conditions reflect a 40 h of labor ($L_{Ref} = 40$ h), a 400 \$ salary payment ($C_{Salary,Ref} = \$ 400$), the 0.8 Ha.w allowance for the use of cultivated area ($U_{CA,Ref} = 0.8$ Ha.w) and a ratio of wildlife area protected of 1.5 times (example value) the cultivated area used (the presumptive ratio (8) $R_{Bio} = 1.5$). To maintain reference conditions, the reference amount of wildlife area must be protected. The wildlife area to be protected is $P_{WA,Ref} = U_{CA,Ref} * R_{Bio} = 0.8 * 1.5 = 1.2$ Ha.w. Wildlife area protection is purchased by the individual and is thus included in the consumption input. For example simplicity, the location based inputs in table 3 are combined with the individual consumption. Under reference conditions, the reference amounts of labor hours worked, cultivated area used and wildlife area protected are removed from the supply chain as individual sustainable absorption (ISA). The Impacts of the labor output are calculated as the sum of inputs minus the ISA outputs. The labor output reflects reference conditions. Expressed per unit time, hours worked can be expressed as a labor intensity of 40 h/w, an environmental impact rate ($L/w = P/w$) of zero Ha and a salary rate of 400 \$/w.

+ Consumption + LBI inputs:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [40 , 0.8 , 1.2] [400].
+ Own work hour input:	[L]	= [40]
- ISA output:	[L, U, P]	= [40 , 0.8 , 1.2]
= Labor output:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [40 , 0 , 0] [400]

Table 3: ISCS Impacts for Cultivated Area used, expressed as original variables under reference conditions for a one-week period, as represented by figure 1. Units: Labor hours worked (h), CA used (Ha.w), WA protected (Ha.w) and salary paid (\$).

For Allowance Variables, normalization takes place by dividing each original variable value by the corresponding reference value. For the above example, the reference normal conditions are given in table 4. While derived for Cultivated Area use (an Allowance variable) the same values are found for Historic Damage variables under normalized reference conditions. For Current Damage variables, reference normal conditions are given in table 5. EH-impact values under reference conditions, expressed as original variables, will differ for each type of EH-variable and for each EH-variable within each type. Under normalized reference conditions, all variable values are reduced to zero or unity and only two sets of values exists; one for Allowance and Historic Damage variables (table 2) and a different one for Current Damage variables (see table 5).

+ Consumption + LBI inputs:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1 , 1 , 1] [1]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [1]
- ISA output:	[l, u, p]	= [1 , 0 , 0]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1 , 0 , 0] [1]

Table 4: ISCS Impacts for allowance and historic damage variables under normalized reference conditions, represented by figure 3. While calculated for a specific period, all values are unit-less.

Calculations of Impacts for all goods and services are carried out using the PSCS and are similar to ISCS calculations. EH-impact values for reference conditions cannot be defined for single items, but can be defined for a reference portfolio of all products and services consumed by a reference individual over a defined period like a year, month or week. For this portfolio to meet reference conditions, the Impacts of the product output for the PSCS must match the Impacts for “Consumption + LBI inputs” for the reference ISCS. The impact values for the original variable (Cultivated Area Use) for this reference condition product portfolio are shown in table 6.

+ Consumption + LBI inputs:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1 , 0 , 0] [1]
+ Own work hour input:	[l]	= [1]
- ISA output:	[l, u, p]	= [1 , 0 , 0]
= Labor output:	[l, u, p] [c]	= [1 , 0 , 0] [1]

Table 5: ISCS Impacts for current damage variables under normalized reference conditions, corresponding with the ISCSs shown in figure 5. While calculated for a specific period, all values are unit-less.

The original variable values are normalized by dividing each original variable value by the corresponding reference (or representative) values. The reference normal conditions are given in table 7. While derived for Cultivated Area use (an Allowance variable) the same values are found for Historic Damage variables. Since the own employee

labor impact inputs to the PSCS are zero under reference conditions no impact accumulation takes place over the PSCS and the XID is zero $[u_{XID}] = [0]$.

+ Supplies + LBI inputs:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [40, 0.8, 1.2] [400]
+ Own Employee labor input:	[L, U, P] [C]	= [40, ,]
- XID output:	[U,]	= [0, ,]
= Product or service output	[L, U, P] [C]	= [40, 0.8, 1.2] [400]

Table 6: PSCS Impacts for a reference portfolio of product and services for Cultivated Area used, expressed as original variable values, corresponding to figure 2. Units: Labor hours (h), CA used (Ha.w), WA protected (Ha.w) and salary paid (\$).

+ Supplies + LBI inputs:	L = S = 5 [l, u, p] [c]	= [0.2, 1, 1] [0.2]
+ Own employee labor input:	E = 9 [l, u, p] [c]	= [1, 0, 0]
- XID output:	N = 10 [u,]	= [0, ,]
= Product or service output:	N = 10 [l, u, p] [c]	= [1, 1, 1] [1]

Table 7: PSCS Impacts for allowance and historic damage variables under normalized reference conditions, corresponding with figure 4. See figure 4 for additional description.

+ Supplies + LBI inputs:	L = S = 5 [l, u, p] [c]	= [0.2, 0, 0] [0.2]
+ Own employee labor input:	E = 9 [l, u, p] [c]	= [1, 0, 0]
- XID output:	N = 10 [u,]	= [0, ,]
= Product or service output:	N = 10 [l, u, p] [c]	= [1, 0, 0] [1]

Table 8: PSCS Impacts for current damage variables under normalized reference conditions, corresponding with figure 5.

Since no allowances exist for current damage variables (the “allowance” is zero), no conservation needs to be applied under reference conditions. The reference normal variable values for current damage variables are given in table 8. Calculation of ISA and XID under non-reference conditions is more complex. The various permutations for the ISA and XID calculation will be presented in a separate paper. Various types of sustainabilities are calculated for each of the three types of variables. Examples are resource use sustainability, conservation sustainability, current damage sustainability and historic damage sustainability as well as their combinations. Details of the calculation of sustainabilities for products, services, individuals and organizations will be presented in a separate paper.

5. Discussion and Conclusions

The IMAC system allows the calculation of impacts and sustainabilities for all products, services and individuals using three types of standardized supply chain steps (ESCS) and standardized calculations. Using ESCSs, the measurement and calculation of impacts takes place in real time, reflecting recent changes in impacts along the supply chain. Impacts of products and services thus change until they are sold, while the E-vouchers amounts are daily recalculated based on daily changing costs of conservation. The process is almost entirely automated, resulting in very low costs of determination of impact and E-voucher amounts. IMACS sellers provide E-vouchers for participating products sold to participating end-user consumers, to pay for the costs of conservation. This renders these products & services sold free of impacts. The voucher costs are initially insignificant and provide attractive marketing opportunities. The E-voucher costs as paid to neutralize current damage can be eliminated by selecting participating suppliers and otherwise stopping to create damaging impacts (installing carbon neutral systems, etc.). That is not the case for historic damage done (i.e. the excess of carbon dioxide in atmosphere and oceans and the reduction of and damage to wildlife area). The cost of carbon sequestration as needed to return to pre-industrial atmospheric and oceanic conditions are not insignificant, but are smaller than the savings resulting from a rapid transition to carbon neutral conditions. These costs and savings will be addressed in future papers. Implementation of the IMAC system allows the creation, funding and rapid growth of all types of conservation like CO₂ sequestration, wildlife area protection, restoration and expansion, protection and restoration of water flows (rivers) and amounts (aquifers), reverse osmosis water production, soil & sediment protection and restoration, dike construction for areas likely to flood due to sea level rise and the improvement of human conditions. This may prevent nature from being pushed past tipping points from which no return is possible (2) and potentially allows a relative fast return to pre-industrial environmental conditions, while improving human conditions and saving costs. The IMAC system includes the impacts carried by employee labor. No other methods are capable of doing this, resulting in inaccurate and unrealistic results. When the inputs to an ESCS originate from outputs of other ESCSs, the calculated impacts for products, services and labor are determined with high accuracy. However, since at first

implementation no such ESCS outputs exist, all impact input values need to be estimated using an automated statistical approach. The estimation methods will be presented in a separate paper.

Commercial, renewable energy (especially wind and solar) can be produced at significantly lower costs than fossil fuel energy (8). For homeowners and businesses alike, the cost of solar power is typically lower than utility power and much lower for larger South facing systems, especially after subsidies. While some costs savings will result from a gradual switch from fossil to renewable energy, much larger savings will result for organizations and supply chain layers making a fast transition. For organizations and consumers alike, most carbon emissions can be eliminated by switching to carbon neutral systems (geothermal heat pumps and electric transportation powered by roof mounted solar panels). For households, installation of geothermal heat pumps and solar panels can be done within a week, but will take longer for larger organizations. Participating organizations and end-user-consumers making this switch will have significant savings compared to those who do not. While the examples used focused on Cultivated Area Use and Carbon Dioxide Emissions, the calculation methods apply to all impact variables of all impact groups. Of all types of conservation, carbon sequestration represents the highest costs. Carbon sequestration costs will drop over time from the current 180 -225 \$/tCO₂ sequestered to less than 50 \$/tCO₂ over twenty years. If 100% of consumers and retailers would participate, this would correspond to an initial E-voucher cost of 14% of revenues. In reality these costs are much lower, since vouchers are only made available for participating products purchased by participating end-user consumers. At 1% product participation and 1% end-user participation this would result in $(14\% * 1\% * 1\% =) 0.0014\%$ (10). For retail sales revenues of \$ 1 million per day, this corresponds to \$ 14 per day in voucher costs; an insignificantly small amount. For these 14 \$/day the retailer can now advertise “*When you participate, we will pay all costs of your available E-conservation for all participating products you buy*”. This would provide a strong marketing message, likely at much lower costs per dollar additional sales compared to other marketing methods.

Once product and end-user participation each reach 10% after about five years, this would increase the E-voucher costs to 0.12% of revenues in case no E-impact reduction measures were taken. The voucher costs will increase for higher participation rates, but will drop to zero after installation and use of carbon neutral systems. These investments will be fully earned back by supply chain savings. In case the retailer installed carbon neutral systems at start of participation (heat pumps, electric transportation and solar panels to provide the annual power needs), his equivalent costs of power drop drastically, while the building related C-sequestration costs (and the associated voucher costs) drop to zero. With a pay-back time of 5 -7 years, carbon neutral system savings would exceed voucher costs. Selection of more favorable carbon neutral system options (geothermal instead of air source heat pumps), favorable installation (south facing orientation for solar panels) and selection of favorable buildings (well insulated and with ample roof surface area available for solar panels) further reduces costs of power and vouchers. The installation of residential carbon neutral systems can be completed within a few days. For retail stores or other businesses, such systems are larger, requiring longer installation periods. Cost and savings aspects will be presented in a separate paper. In case of 100% participating suppliers and employees along the supply chain selling only participating goods and services, each supplier provides all E-vouchers (or the monetary equivalent) to neutralize impacts of all products/supplies sold. Each participating organization thus only needs to provide additional E-vouchers to neutralize E-impacts of their own organization’s PSCSs. Without participating suppliers, the first participating retailers pay all E-voucher costs. While these costs are initially very low (0.0012% of revenues, see above), each participant organization would benefit from selecting participating supplies and employees as rapidly as possible. Using the standardized ESCSs, the E-voucher cost to be paid to customer organization can easily be calculated at the end of each day. The costs savings from a 100% change to carbon neutrality are large, while the remaining carbon sequestration voucher costs are zero. However, a 100% change to carbon neutrality is initially impossible since this would require 100% carbon neutral supplies and 100% carbon neutral employees. The same applies to all other impact variables and to all upstream products, services and employees.

This would change once historic damage is included. Anticipated IMACS related costs and savings will be presented in a separate paper, but data indicate that the energy costs savings in the commercial sector are much larger than the C-sequestration costs paid. C-sequestration costs can be paid out of energy savings along the supply chain (12). Customer participation can be so high that the far majority of the supply chain follows their customers and also participates; paying the C-sequestration costs becomes the new normal. Otherwise, retailer and supply chain spending on C-sequestration will need to be tax refunded for historic CO₂ emissions.

Since the impacts of employees are added to other impacts of organizations, organizations have an interest in offering employees residences with sustainable impacts (carbon negative, low areas use and water consumptions, etc.). participating organizations in the same town/city would benefit in combining efforts building low to high income residences on a not-for-profit basis. This would accelerate urban renewal and make more residences available for all income groups.

6. Methods

Under the Environmental Impact Measurement and Conservation System (IMACS), impact variables are organized in eleven metric impact groups (see table 1). Conserving impacts can be in the same metric impact group or in a different one. For example, the conserving impact for *cultivated area use* is *wildlife area protection* which is found in the metric impact group *biodiversity change*. For most other impacts, use, damage and conserving impacts are found in the same metric impact group. Impacts can be a function of multiple variables. For example; climate change impacts are represented by a separate variable for each greenhouse gas emitted (carbon dioxide, methane, N₂O, fluorinated gasses) and can be combined as carbon dioxide equivalent values. Sequestered CO₂ is a conserving E-impact variable part of the same impact group.

Three types of neutral or damaging impact variables are used: *Allowance*, *Current damage* and *Historic damage*.

- *Allowance* variables, representing use of natural resources for which a per capita maximum usage exists (the *allowance*). The use of each natural resource is only sustainable if the use is equal or less than the allowance, while a sufficient amount of the natural resource is protected. *Allowance* variables represent pairs (or triples) of variables where the first reflects the resource use and the second (and/or third) reflects the protection and restoration of natural resources and systems.

The ratios of resource protection over resource use vary per variable. Example pairs and triples:

- Use of cultivated area and protection of wildlife area within the same ecoregion, for its biodiversity.
- Use of watershed/precipitation area for its water and protection of watershed/precipitation area for its water quality and amount, and protection of forests to allow evapotranspiration.
- Use of soil/sediments for cultivation purposes and conservation of soils and sediments such that losses & degradation are less than the local natural rates of restoration or formation.
- Use of cultivated area at risk of flooding and dike protection of a cultivated area against flooding such that flooding risks of the cultivated area are very low.
- Use of cultivated area at risk of flooding and dike protection of a wildlife area at risk of flooding within the same ecoregion, such that flooding risks of the wildlife area are extremely low.
- *Current damage* variables reflect damage done since a globally set date (say 1/1/2025) and include restoration variables. No allowances exist for current damage variables. Examples:
 - inhumane conditions and rehabilitation to human conditions,
 - current CO₂ emissions and current CO₂ sequestration,
 - current wildlife area loss and current wildlife area restoration,
 - current fresh water extraction (rivers, aquifers) and current restoration of flows and volumes
 - current damage to and loss of soil and sediments and their current restoration
 - current loss of coastal land at risk of flooding and their reclamation after flooding
- *Historic damage* variables, reflecting damage done prior to a globally set date (say 1/1/2025). No allowances exist, but instead requirements exist for historic damage variables. Examples:
 - historic CO₂ emissions and current CO₂ sequestration of the historic emissions
 - historic wildlife area loss and current wildlife area restoration and expansion of the historic lost area
 - historic damage to and loss of soil and sediments and their current restoration
 - historic fresh water extraction (rivers, aquifers) and current restoration of flows and volumes
 - historic loss of coastal land at risk of flooding and their reclamation after flooding

Participants: Participation in the IMAC system is voluntary. Two types of participants are defined: individuals and organizations. All participants other than individuals are categorized as organizations.

The IMACS system distinguishes two types of products: the product of individual labor (*labor product* or *labor*) and *goods and services*. Labor and goods and services are each represented by dedicated environmental supply chain steps (ESCSs), each with inputs and outputs. Individuals working for themselves are working as an employee for their own organization. For IMACS, the words “organizations”, “producers” and “service providers” are used as synonyms. A producer is usually defined as *an organization that makes, supplies or otherwise provides goods, commodities or services for sale or other distribution*. Under the IMACS the definition of producers is extended to all entities providing goods, services or anything else distributed to others. Governments are producers of laws and services. Schools are producers of educational products and services. Broadcasting organizations and publishers distribute information. Charities provide products and services for the common good. Retailers are the producers most of us see on a daily basis.

Someone receiving money as wages/salary is a worker producing labor. But this concept of receiving income in exchange for producing a labor product is extended under the IMACS. Retirees receiving a pension receive this as a

delayed payment of income for work done in prior years and continue to be categorized as employees. Under the IMACS (and for the purpose of calculation) the category of employees is extended to all individual receivers of income, even if the number of hours worked is low or zero and even in absence of any prior employment history between payer of income and payee (investors, welfare receivers, etc.). In order to simplify and standardize the IMACS calculations, all payers of income are treated as employers while all receivers of income are treated as their employees. Defined in this way all adult individuals have their own ISCS.

Location Based Impacts: All environ-human (EH) impacts take place at a specific location and are referred to as *location-based impacts* (LBI). LBIs are all Impacts not yet included in purchases or labor (e.g. use of land as cultivated area, extraction of raw material, emissions). Once LBIs are used as input to an environ-human supply chain step (ESCS), they become part of the impacts of labor, product or service.

Environmental Supply Chain step (ESCS): ESCSs are used to calculate the Impacts of products, services and individual labor. ESCS figures read like *process flow diagrams* (PFD) used in the chemical industry, although there are differences. In process flow diagrams (PFDs) a “single line” represents flow in one direction while in ESCSs two directional flows can be represented by a “single line”. Mass flow values for the various chemical components in PFDs are replaced by various EH impact flow values in ESCSs. While mass and energy balances apply in PFD calculation, EH impact and financial balances apply in ECSC calculations. Different from PFDs, where equipment has volume, ESCS elements (unless specified) have no volume. Only designated storage elements have volume (and/or storage capacity) in ESCS figures. The “*financial account*” blocks shown in figure 9 at both sides of the supply chain step represent the same account used for receiving and paying money but are shown twice for clarity. In other figures the existence of these storage blocks is implied but none are shown. For all types of ESCS, all outputs Impacts are calculated directly from the input Impacts.

Individual Supply Chain Step (ISCS): An ISCS represents input and output impacts of one individual. ISCSs have three inputs: human conditions, impacts of products and services consumed and LBIs. ISCSs have two outputs: *individual sustainable absorption* (ISA) and the labor product. Of all human conditions that are inputs to ISCS, only the labor hours worked and wages paid are always carried. The ISA allows removal from the supply chain of matching amounts of EH resource use and EH protection applied. ISA also allows removal from the supply chain of matching amounts of damage done and restored. Such removal of matching amounts of EH use & damage and EH restoration impact is needed to prevent supply chain accumulation of such impacts (figure 3). Since at early stages of implementation no human condition inputs other than labor hours are used, no other variable symbols or values are indicated for this input at this stage. Note that the salary paid appears as part of the labor output. See “*Single and Bi-directional Flow*”.

Product Supply Chain Step (PSCS): A PSCS represents the input and output Impacts of a single product or service a series of identical products or services. PSCSs have three inputs: labor, supplies and LBIs. PSCS have two outputs, one for the *excess impact deduction* (XID) and one for the Impacts of the single or series of identical products made or services provided. In almost all cases waste is produced that needs to be rendered harmless by a waste processor requiring more EH inputs and payments. In that case the waste processing service provided becomes an input to the PSCS for the product or service produced. All Impacts of the process, including the waste produced and treated, are assigned to the product. When different products are made at one location, each represents a different PSCS. In that case the inputs and waste are assigned to the different PSCSs on an equitable basis (like proportional to sales volume in dollars). Products include among others: fresh water withdrawn, materials extracted/mined, non-wild animals, modified materials, parts, consumer products and their assemblages, real estate, infrastructure, protected wildlife areas, protected water withdrawal areas, sequestered carbon and any material asset offered for sale or that changes ownership. Services include financial services (providing investment capital, loans and other financial assets) and anything else representing a financial or non-material environmental value (the title to having provided carbon sequestration, wildlife area conservation, human condition rehabilitation).

Rating Supply Chain Step (RSCS): Impacts originating from ESCS calculations represent the most accurate Impacts and can directly be used as inputs to downstream ESCSs. This is not the case for “unrated” Impacts (inputs not originating from an ESCS). Impacts of supplies/inputs originating from non-participating sellers and non-participating employees, first need to be quantified by an Impact Rating Organization (IRO). Each IRO rating for a single item or batch of items or for individual labor, forms its own rating supply chain step (RSCS) as shown in figure 6 for an individual supply chain step (ISCS) and figure 7 for a product supply chain step (PSCS). With increasing societal participation, the fraction of ESCSs in the supply chain will increase (ideally to 100%) and RSCS

ratings will be limited to initial location-based impacts (LBI) assessments and periodic updates to cover LBI changes. In figures, the vertical dashed line indicates the border between the unrated (left) and rated (right) sides of the figure. All inputs to the PSCS that do not originate from an ESCS (“unrated” inputs), first pass through the RSCS and exit as “rated” impact. The RSCS brings its own impacts for LBI, supplies and own labor (in red). The far majority of impacts to the RSCS are client PSCS impacts passing through, while being rated. Unrated impacts consumed by an IRO need to be determined by an independent IRO. The sum of RSCS impacts and original PSCS impacts passing through (in red), form the new supplies impacts to the client PSCS. See figures 6 and 7.

Representation: Each labor output represents a single individual and is the result of individual consumption choices. The individual supply chain step (ISCS) thus represents the environ-human (EH) impacts of the individual. This is different for products and services of organizations. Especially during the transition period, participant organizations may not have all products and services rated. Products part of the same production series are represented by the same product supply chain step (PSCS). However, such products following a different route to consumers (via different distributors or retailers) end up via different and new PSCSs to the point of sale to end-user consumers and end up with different Impacts. Products can be non-sustainable while made by sustainable organizations (but it is harder to do the reverse). A PSCS represents the Impacts of a product or service but does not represent the Impacts of the organization selling it.

Figure 6: A Rating Supply Chain Steps (RSCS) is used to quantify EH impacts that are inputs to an ISCS.

Single and Bi-directional Flow: The wording used for inputs and outputs of environmental supply chain steps (ESCSs) are defined based on flow direction of the entity represented. Materials and supplies consumed as well as products made are indicated in figures to flow in end-user direction; from left to right. Financial investment and loans are supplies to each ESCS (a supply of money) and also flow from left to right. Financial compensations such as salary and payments for products purchased, flow in resource (or compensation) direction; from right to left. All products and labor are inputs to ESCS and flow in end-user direction, while salary paid and payments made for products purchased are inputs to ESCS and flow in resource direction (see figures 3, 4 and 5). The term

“downstream” is used to indicate the material flow through the supply chain from resource to consumer (left to right in figures), while the term “upstream” is used to indicate the financial compensation flow in resource direction (from right to left in figures).

Conservation Applied: Under the IMACS, conservation applied by an individual or organization is conservation “consumed”: conservation applied cannot be resold or credited to other products or services. Humans consume resources, do EH damage directly and indirectly, and can apply EH conservation with the products they consume. Products store resources used, damage done and conservation applied until the product is consumed by individuals or organizations.

Figure 7: A Rating Supply Chain Step (RSCS) is used to quantify EH impacts that are inputs to a PSCS.

Work Hours and Salary: For individuals, labor hours worked and salaries paid are among the most important human condition variables. All income received by individuals (e.g., salary, pension, investment returns, unemployment benefit, welfare, gifts) is treated as compensation, irrespective of hours worked. The world’s very poor not receiving sufficient compensation (reflecting inhumane conditions) are treated as workers who should receive welfare. Minors are treated as supported by their parents and will have their individual allowances assigned to their parents. All adults and homeless/non-supported minors (once identified as such) are treated as both consumers and employees under the IMACS.

All costs paid for products and services sold are ultimately income to someone. Therefore, costs paid for products made and salaries paid for work done are treated the same and both are EH impact variables.

ESCS Lifecycle: Labor (as the product of work done by an individual) and salary paid change over time, but the same ISCS remains associated with a specific individual for a lifetime. This is not the case for PSCS, which have a fleeting life. Each time a product or service is sold or an impact not yet included is added to a product or service, a new PSCS is formed. This does not only happen during manufacturing when labor, materials and energy used are added or removed, but also with change of ownership, and during shipment and storage of the product. Each

downstream ESCS absorbs/consumes the Impacts of the labor, supplies and location-based impacts (LBI) added by upstream ESCSs. If possible to do so in advance, multiple “process” steps can be combined in a single PSCS. This is typically the case for process steps taking place at the same location. A PSCS continues to exist in active form as long as one or more of the products in the series represented by the PSCS exist. Once all products are absorbed by downstream supply chain steps (sold, consumed in downstream manufacturing, written off and treated as waste), the PSCS goes dormant and can only be accessed for historical data retrieval.

Display of Variables and Values in ESCS Figures: With 50 to 100 EH variables in use at full implementation, not all variables or their values can be shown in ESCS without obscuring the figures. The number of variables shown in figures is therefore limited to the following four: L, U_m, P_n and C. L and C represent respectively the labor hours worked and the salary paid. U_m represents all EH damage and natural resource use variables, while P_n represents all EH conservation variables (in both cases for all eleven EH impact groups). Showing U_m and P_n would represent all variables, while showing the variable symbol without subscripts (U and P) would represent specific variables as specified in the accompanying text. Specific variables could also be indicated using a multi-letter subscript specified in the accompanying text. While part of variable groups U_m and P_n, variables L (labor hours worked) and C (wages or price paid) are two of the most important human condition variables that are always included in the series of four variables shown. Variables L and C also indicate product scale. E.g. for a standard work week of 40 hours, working L = 80 h per week would represent exceeding labor hours. Analogously, a C = \$ 300 weekly income would represent only 60% of a (say) \$ 500 weekly local “living wage”. When it is known that the employee labor hours spent and income paid were average, a product with L = 80 h and C = \$ 1,000 would both indicate that it took two average labor weeks and the average salary to make the product (providing scale).

Directional Grouping of Variables: The four variables used in text and figures are indicated as: [L, U_m, P_n] | [C]. The two groups of (three and one) variables are grouped using square brackets [] and separated by a vertical bar “ | ”, while in figures arrows below or above the variable groups indicate the flow direction for each variable group. See figures 3, 4 and 5. L, U_m and P_n thus flow in consumer direction (left to right), while C flows in resource direction (right to left). Note that all inputs and outputs are represented by single horizontal lines (as used in figures 3 to 5) to indicate variables for which product and labor flows flow in consumer direction and financial compensation (payments for products and salaries) flows in resource direction. In figures, variable values are written directly above or below the corresponding variable letters. Streams without financial compensation have no value for compensation variable C, and the letter C and number are left out. Since under the IMACS environ-human (EH) impacts are only allowed to flow in consumer direction (left to right in figures), all payments C made by participants are free of Impacts.

Reference Conditions: The theoretical individual living 100% sustainable with respect to all EH impact variables, working the standard number of hours and earning the per capita global income, is referred to as living under *reference conditions*. Normalized reference conditions for the total of all consumption for the reference individual differ per variable type: allowance variables, current damage variables and historic damage variables.

- For allowance variables, the normalized reference condition values for the total of all individual consumption (goods and services purchased plus location based impacts) correspond to [l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1].
- For current EH damage variables, the normalized reference condition values for the total of all individual consumption correspond to [l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1].
- Historic damage parameters behave similar to allowance parameters, but with the difference that in order to reach 100% sustainability on the variable, a minimum amount needs to be restored compared to the maximum amount that can be used for allowance parameters. For historic EH damage variables, per capita annual restoration requirements (U_{m,ref}) are calculated based on the technical minimum restoration period. The per capita annual restoration values are further modified as function of income c_i of individual i. While U_{m,ref} reflects the historical damage for variable U_m for the reference individual, U_{m,Indi} = c_i * U_{m,ref} represents the historical damage for variable U_m used for individual i with income c_i. Expressed under normalized conditions: u_{m,Indi} = c_i. To live sustainable with respect to historic damage variables, all historic damage needs to be restored (p_{m,Indi} = u_{m,Indi}). Normalized conditions, 100% sustainable with respect to conservation for historic damage variables, correspond to [l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1] for the reference individual and to [l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 5, 5] | [5] for the individual with income c_i = C / C_{ref} = 5.

Presumptive and Measured Conservation Ratio: The world is divided in ecoregions; relatively large areas of land or water where the probability of encountering different species and communities at any given location remains

relatively constant. In order for cultivated area to be sustainably available, a certain fraction of wildlife area within the same ecoregion must be protected for its biodiversity.

The ratio $R_{Bio} = P_{region} / U_{region}$ represents the lowest ratio of wildlife area (WA) protected and cultivated area (CA) used where biodiversity losses in the particular ecoregion would remain zero. In the normalized case, the minimum required wildlife area to be protected is $p_{WA} = u_{CA} * R_{Bio}$. The ratio R_{Bio} can be a presumptive ratio (default) or a ratio based on actual measurements (after adequate studies). In order to live sustainably with respect to conservation, sufficient wildlife area (WA) needs to be protected for its biodiversity. Presumptive ratios are set for fresh water extraction (R_{Water}), soil use, degradation and loss (R_{Soil}) and any other resource use variable for which allowances can be set under conditions of adequate resource conservation. The values for the presumptive conservation ratios for each resource use variable are set to values significantly higher (average plus 2 - 3 sigma) than the values expected after actual field study measurements, by a group or independent scientists who are experts in each field of natural resource use and conservation (9). After field study measurements, the presumptive ratio is lowered to the measured ratio.

Primary (1st) and 2nd Order Effects: Some types of environmental damage affect future environmental damage due to feedback effects. In some cases, it affects the same type of damage and in other cases different types of damage. For example, anthropogenic carbon dioxide emissions lead to both increase growth of forests and global warming (1st order effect). Immediate sequestration of carbon dioxide would prevent both. Any delay in C-sequestration causes an increase in C-emissions as feedback due to:

- Accelerated melting of permafrost and the subsequent release of methane and CO₂
- Increased C-emissions due to increased digestion of stored carbon in soils at higher temperatures.

Such increases are added to the individual C-emissions accounts. Similar 2nd order effects apply to other types of current damage (e.g. biodiversity loss). Similar to current damage, 2nd order effects apply to delayed conservation for allowance variables and for delayed restoration for historic damage variables. The determinations of 1st and 2nd order effects need to be carried out for all EH variables in all eleven EH impact groups listed in section 7.2. This implies that emissions of 1 tC not immediately sequestered requires a future C-sequestration much larger than 1 tC to reach the same atmospheric effect over the next 200 years.

Restoration Capacity Effects: To restore environmental damage, a capacity to restore such damage is needed. For example, a section of virgin wildlife area destroyed (cultivated) may recover 50% of its virgin species populations in 100 year and 99% in 300 years if adjacent to an unaffected virgin wildlife area section. For 20% of global land in virgin wildlife condition and 20% land area under constant wildlife restoration, an annual loss of 0.066% of virgin wildlife area (and a 300-year period to 100% restoration) would result in no net restoration of wildlife area. The wildlife area restoration capacity is thus limited and requires very low losses to be effective (11). For carbon sequestration the restoration capacity is limited by the rate at which humanity can build C-sequestration capacity as needed to reach year 1750 atmospheric carbon dioxide conditions.

Normalized Reference Conditions for ISCS: The total consumption input of individual supply chain steps (ISCSs) is the sum of products and location-based impacts (LBI) consumed over the assessment period. The normalized reference condition values for allowance and historic EH damage variables for the total consumption of ISCSs happen to be the same, but differ for current damage variables (see figures 3, 4 and 5).

Reference consumption total for allowance and historic damage variables: $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1]$.

Reference consumption total for current damage variables: $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1]$.

Reference ISA for allowance and historic damage variables: $[l, u, p] = [1, 1, 1]$.

Reference ISA for current damage variables: $[l, u, p] = [1, 0, 0]$.

Looking at the labor outputs of the ISCS to the product supply chain step (PSCS) in figures 3 to 5, normalized reference labor conditions for all three variable types correspond to: $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1]$

This means that 100% sustainable labor is always free of Impacts. (See § 7.4 for ISA calculations)

Individual Income and Sustainability Distribution

Incomes are not normally distributed either currently or in an on average sustainable society, but the following illustration is easier to follow if we assume so. For a normally distributed income in an on average 100% sustainable world, exactly half the population would live more than 100% sustainable while the other half would live less than 100% sustainable. Under those conditions the unused natural resource allowances available to the lower income half of the population are used by the higher income half of the world population.

Combined ISCS-PSCS: No single set of normalized reference condition input values exist for the combination of location-based impacts (LBI) and supply inputs to product supply chain steps (PSCS). For each supply chain step the calculation needs to be carried out for each variable u from the group u_m and for each corresponding variable p from group p_n . When shown as a combined ISCS-PSCS, ISCSs are typically shown as a group of ISCSs. The grouped ISCS representation is used to reduce space requirements in figures. Unless all employees are identical, the individual sustainable absorption (ISA) for allowance variables can only be correctly calculated by doing so separately for each individual supply chain step (ISCS), after which all results are combined. Comparing the same variables types, normalized reference product outputs for PSCS have identical impact variable presentations as the normalized reference total consumption inputs for ISCSs:

Reference product output for allowance and historic damage variables: $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1]$.

Reference product output for current damage variables: $[l, u, p] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1]$.

See additional explanation under “*Product Portfolio*”.

Use of Multipliers: For combined ISCS-PSCSs (figure 5), the multipliers E , S , L and N are used in combination with environ-human (EH) variable notation $[l, u, p] | [c]$, where each multiplier operates at both sides of the vertical bar “|”. E = number of own employees, S = units of supplies, L = units of location-based impact (LBI) while N is the number of products produced. An individual supply chain step (ISCS, as in figure 3) represents a single individual and no multipliers are used. For group-ISCSs, the multiplier E is used for all inputs and outputs.

Product Portfolio: Individuals consume a large number of mostly different products during a year. A product supply chain step (PSCS) represents a single or series of identical products and services. However, it is sometimes easier to visualize the interaction of in- and outflows of environmental supply chain steps (ISCS and PSCS) by imagining that this single product or services is a reference (or other) portfolio of many products and services as consumed over one year by an individual. Instead of one annual portfolio, one could also imagine 12 identical monthly portfolios, each of 1/12 of the annual portfolio size, delivered at your doorstep by your favorite retailer at the 1st of each month. It could also be a daily identical portfolio (all daily items in one box) of 1/365th of the annual portfolio size. In that case, the multiplier N represents the number of such portfolio boxes produced. For the reference individual this would be a reference portfolio. These reference portfolios, while identical with respect to the total of Impacts, can still represent an infinite combination of different collections of good and services. In almost all cases, a mix of LBI and supplies is used as input to each PSCS (in addition to labor), but theoretically, only LBI or only supplies could be used (in addition to labor) for a particular PSCS. L and S then represent the number of batches of respectively LBI and supplies used to make these N portfolios, such that $S = N$ when $L = 0$ and $L = N$ when $S = 0$. Using this convention, the values for $[l, u, p] | [c]$ in the LBI and supplies inputs to the PSCS are sized in proportion to those used in the (reference or other) product portfolios and can more easily be followed throughout the combined ISCS-PSCS diagram.

While the use of product portfolios facilitates the understanding of supply chain diagrams and calculations, these diagrams and calculations remain the same if used for smaller amounts purchased, with the only difference that all values for $[l, u, p] | [c]$ representing inputs and outputs of ESCS are smaller numbers.

As is illustrated in figure 5, under reference conditions the normalized EH impact variable values for products consumed by the individuals part of the grouped ISCS are represented by $[l, u_m, p_n] | [c] = [1, 0, 0] | [1]$ for current damage variables. These are the same for the product or service output of the PSCS, since these are the same products or services (or their portfolios). Analogous, the reference normal representation for products and services (or their portfolios) for allowance and historic damage variables is $[l, u_m, p_n] | [c] = [1, 1, 1] | [1]$ and is the same for products and services consumed by reference individuals. As explained above, the numerical values for these representations are the same when expressed yearly, monthly or daily and thus independent of the period selected. Note that not only the internal EH balances in figure 5 are closing (over each ESCS) but also the external balance closes. All $N = 10$ “Products of Organization” are consumed by the $E = 9$ employees as “Products Consumed” plus the “hidden” ($E = 1$) employee that provided the supplies. The latter can be calculated from the “Supplies” input, since $S [l, u_m, p_n] | [c] = 5 [0.2, 0, 0] | [0.2]$ represents $S * l = 5 * 0.2 = 1$ and $S * c = 5 * 0.2 = 1$, both representing one employee, bringing the total to $N = E + 1 = 9 + 1 = 10$.

Hidden ISA outflow: Hidden in figure 5 is the ISA outflow of the single employee ISCS providing the supplies to the PSCS. This is caused by the fact that the upstream supply chain section is not shown. The total ISA outflow is thus: $E+1 [l, u_m, p_n] = 10 [1, 0, 0]$ for current damage variables and $E+1 [l, u_m, p_n] = 10 [1, 1, 1]$ for allowance and historic damage variables. Note that the total EH balance of inputs and outputs over the combined ISCS-PSCS

also closes: employee hours to ISCS and Supplies, LBI to PSCS and Supplies to PSCS, are equal to the total outflows as individual sustainable absorption (ISA).

LBIs values set to zero: LBIs represent Impacts without labor hours spent or compensation paid. For labor hours and compensation $\neq 0$, the impact should be included under “supplies”. Therefore, compensation variable [c] is not shown, while variable l_{LBI} is always set to zero. For simplicity of illustration, all LBI inputs to the ISCS in figure 5 are set to zero ($[l, u_m, p_n]_{LBI} = [0, 0, 0]$). A reference individual renting a carbon neutral high-rise apartment can have zero LBI inputs, when all Impacts “consumed” are covered by payments made. The same applies to PSCSs in case all LBI sources are covered by “paid for” services (rental of retail of office space, including utilities and waste handling).

Individual and Product Data Sheet: All individuals have a unique identification (ID) number representing themselves and their labor. This ID is associated with their ISCS data sheet. Similar to a bank account, this data is only accessible to the individual. In addition to financial data, impact values are added for all transactions. The individual can give the employer (revocable) access to a limited subset of these data. Likewise, each PSCS representing a particular manufactured product or service has a unique product ID number. Each product copy, part of the same product series (with a unique serial number), has a unique product ID number (within the series). The PSCS ID number gives access to the product data sheet containing all pertinent data like description, EH variable values, serial numbers, number of copies within the series and product ID numbers of all copies in the series. All data sheets of marketed products are in turn stored in a database, are public and can be accessed to allow consumers to compare impact and prices of products.

Data Transmission between ESCS and Database: During each sales transaction, the unique product ID number tag is electronically read, linking the product to its product data sheet. During the transaction, all pertinent data are transmitted as a collection of elements $A = \{a, b, c, \dots, zz\}$ between the seller’s terminal, the regional database and sellers and buyers accounts. Alternatively, only the product ID is transmitted and all data needed are extracted at both ends from the product data sheet. As part of the transaction, EH impacts values are deducted from the seller’s account while the same values are added to the buyer’s account. The EH variable values of the item purchased are not based on the data as provided by the seller (which could be an incorrect data set), but originate from global, regional or local databases. For every item in the product series sold, the total of unsold items is reduced by one unit during the sale transaction. Selling of products previously sold or selling counterfeits is thus impossible. Note that otherwise identical products (copies), part of the same original production series, that follow a different supply chain path (e.g. sold by different sellers) will collect different impact variable values (creating a new PSCS) and are no longer copies under the IMACS, but represent different products.

Use of Storage Blocks: Inputs and outputs of environmental supply chain steps (ESCSs) often do not represent continuous flows and where continuous, are not always delivered as a constant flow, while billing is never a constant flow. Individual income earned is in part saved to be spent in later years. Any accumulation of money or assets is a form of financial storage. End-user consumers typically store products while large purchases are made that are consumed over years or decades (appliances, cars, buildings). Where appropriate and desired, virtual (electronic) storage blocks should be used to even out Impacts over time. Virtual storage blocks are also used for product outflows in case products are stored prior to sale or used for recycling and waste treatment (see figure 9). In most figures, storage blocks are implied but not shown.

Use of Units: For C-emissions, each product sold must be assigned a C-emission amount, expressed in kg. Since amounts must be expressed in the same units to allow conversion free addition and subtraction in ESCS calculations, all C-emissions ESCS inputs and outputs must be expressed in the same units of mass (e.g. kg, ton). However, to calculate individual sustainability, the individual C-emission averages are compared to the national or global average individual emissions, both calculated over the same time period. Therefore, to calculate individual sustainability with respect to C-emissions, the units used are kg/period or ton/period. The likely most used options are: tonCO₂/year, tonCO₂/month, kgCO₂/week and kgCO₂/day.

For CA use, the area used both increases with the area of the plot used and the time of its usages. Each product produced must be expressed in units reflecting “area * period”. For use of original variables, the likely most used options are Ha.y, m².y and m².d. Since amounts must be expressed in the same units to be added and subtracted easily in the ESCS calculations, all ESCS inputs and outputs must be expressed in the same units like m².d or equivalent options. However, to calculate individual sustainability, individual CA use averages are compared to national or global averages for individual CA use, both expressed over the same time period. Therefore, to calculate

individual sustainability with respect to CA use, the units used are area*period/period. The likely most used options are: Ha.y/y (= Ha), m².y/y (= m²), m².month/month (= m²), m².w/w (= m²) and m².d/d (= m²). Expressed as normalized variables, all variables are unit-less and no requirement to list units or periods exists.

Variable Type	Example Variable Used	Variable and Units for Product, Service or Labor	Variable and Units for Individual over Period	
			Day	Week
Current Damage	CO2 emissions	U (kg)	U per day (kg/d)	U per week (kg/w)
Historic Damage	CO2 emissions	U (kg)	U per day (kg/d)	U per week (kg/w)
Allowance	Cultivated Area Use	U (m ² .d)	U per day (m ²)	U per week (m ²)
Allowance	Labor hours	L (h)	L per day (h/d)	L per week (h/w)
Allowance	Salary paid	S (\$)	S per day (\$/d)	S per week (\$/w)

Table 8: Variables indicated by their customary letters and expressed in their units for selected periods, for current damage, historic damage and allowance variables as used in ESCS figures and associated tables and calculations.

7. References

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- Future editing note: Find and recheck this Excel calculation.
- Future editing note: Find spreadsheet with calculated energy spending in the commercial sector. I recall the value was ~ 17%, much larger than retailer spending in C-sequestration in the peak DACCS cost year. Add a reference to the paper where I reported that.
